

**Physics *in* the Metaphysics of Alexander Papadiamantes :
“To The Christ Of The Castle”**

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Abstract

The unanimously respected by generations of Readers and Experts as the “Saint of Greek Letters” Alexander Papadiamantes (1851 – 1911), the prime enthusiast of the miraculous beauty of Nature and of the deficiency-compensating Grace of the Divine Saviour in post-1821, liberated-Nation, Hellenic Literature, is an inexhaustible melodious fountain of decent literary delight and beneficial existential devoutness. The current Study is locating and attempting to characterise major Signs of an idiosyncratic and existentially original interweaving of (subconscious) functionality of notional Physics and genuine Piety in his Opus through investigating his celebrated Christmas Narrative “To The Christ Of The Castle” (1892).

Keywords:

Alexander Papadiamantes, Physics, Metaphysics, Physical Philosophy, Science & Religion, Ethnicity & Culture, Prose, Narrative.

1. Introduction

Alexander Papadiamantes, the Poetic Writer of the Hellenic New Athenian School of Literature (1880 – 1920), was born in the Island of Skiathos (lying between Magnesia and the Chalcidike triple Peninsula) in 1851 to decent Priest Adamantius Emmanuel's family of ultimately seven children.

Having attended School successively in Skiathos, Scopelos, Chalcis, Piraeus, and Athens (The National Benefactor Varvaces School) and having followed Philologist Studies at the National and Capodistrian University of Athens, he began acting as a Chronicler and contributing both (Anglo-Hellenic and Franco-Hellenic) Literature Translation and (in serial presentation) his own evolving Opus to the Literary Section of the then recently founded and already famous Newspaper *Acropolis*. Later on, a parallel regular co-operation of his with *To Asty* (The Polis), the other renowned Athenian Newspaper of noble cultural standards in that epoque, was inaugurated to be also being fruitfully performed up to his passing away (1911), a dormition which bequeathed to the Cosmos of Letters 138 Narratives, 7 Novels and 14 Poems.

Papadiamantes has been being widely known and loved by virtue mainly of his Narratives (especially his Christmas and Easter Narratives, all capable of inimitably offering a Psyche Catharsis conducive to believing in cherishing the Divine Mysteries), which are permeated by a charismatic convolution of authentic adoration for the Beauty of Nature (portrayed through his frequent lyric description of village, mountain and littoral sites of his native Island) and for Christ The Saviour, on the one hand, and of profound psychological anatomy of the characters of his Heroes (for which Quality he has been recognised by Experts as “the Greek Dostoyevsky”), on the other. His genuine, brave and convincing devotion to Byzantine-Culture Christianity and to the unreplaceable value of pure Patriotic Tradition, Ethics and Customs as eternally remaining vitally sacred for every post-1821 generation of Hellenism has induced to his any-era Readers and Opus Researchers the ever-felt devout enthusiasm of recognising him as “The Saint of Greek Letters”.

It is worth mentioning that the Nobel-Laureate (1979) Prominent Greek Poet Odysseus Elytes (1911 – 1996), the astoundingly joyful Herald primarily of the Splendour of his Country's Sky Light and Sea Colour as intensely energising in parallel his Eros for the Woman and the National Memory of and Alertness for Independence-Defence eternal Marathon-wise and Pindos-echoing Bravery, has in one of his Apothegmatic Essays

urged the Hellenes to recall in practice the Paradigm of historically right faithful and patriotic Ethos of Papadiamantes, whenever they are faced with any evil ordeal of either foreign or domestic origin; that the Alexandrian Hellenic-Diaspora universally eponymous Poet, Constantine Cavafy (1863 – 1933), has characterised Papadiamantes as “the Summit of Summits” in the landscape of post-1821 Hellenic Prose-Writing; that the Founder (1927) and first Editor-in-Chief of the still being edited and diachronically most prestigious and authoritative Hellenic Literary Journal *New Hestia*, Prose and Theatrical Writer (and as of 1931 Member of the Academy of Athens) Gregory Xenopoulos (1867 – 1951), has documented in a spontaneous Encomium issued upon the Papadiamantean sleeping-in-the-Lord that “Papadiamantes has never lied in any belief, has never feigned any feeling, his style has never imitated any other; instead, he has always minted gold coins in favour of his Readers from the inexhaustible mine of his pure and immaculate Psyche”. Moreover, later assessments [1 – 4] of his Personality and Opus converge clearly to the above.

As regards, now, the essence of dramatic evolution of his Christmas Narrative “To The Christ Of The Castle” (1892), having been selected for our investigation in the present Study, it is interestingly deduced that Physical Phenomena, mostly wild, are rather fueling than decelerating the earnest eagerness of the Heroes of the Essay as to their putting into full action the decision for a tempestuous but, through empirically exploiting proper Physical Laws, dexterously navigated boat travel needed for a pious peregrine and rescuing Christmas-Day visit to the ancient Acropolis of the Periphery of their (and the Author’s) Birthplace Village on Skiathos. In conjunction, the ethical sweetness experienced upon their successful arrival at the historical, yet rather abandoned Citadel Church of the Nativity of Christ, especially as ignited by the impressive metaphysical scintillation of the Frescoes and the Temple Icons, and furthermore during the Christmas Liturgy and Divine Eucharistia ministered by the leader of their demanding winter mission, the devoted and inspiring Priest of their native Village, is being found as worth both mentioning and interpreting.

Each following Excerpt of the Papadiamantean Opus has been downloaded from the Website of the Corpus of his Writings (www.papadiamantis.org), whereas the Translation (concerning both these Excerpts and the Kontakion), free at some points but constantly careful in respecting the Papadiamantean overall Style and his rising frequent Message, has been attempted by the Investigator of this Study.

2. Physics *in* the Metaphysics of Alexander Papadiamantes

2.1 The Metaphysical Scintillation of the Holy Icons

Scene following the adventurous arrival of the Faithful Excursionists at the ancient Acropolis (achieved after their braving a tempestuous Sea and a snowstorm-overloaded, long helical inclined pedestrian-path):

«... , κ' ἐγέμισαν ἄνθρακας τὸ μέγα πύραυνον, τὸ σωζόμενον ἐντὸς τοῦ ἱεροῦ βήματος, κ' ἔθεσαν τὸ πύραυνον ἐν τῷ μέσῳ τοῦ ναοῦ, ρίψασαι ἄφθονον λίβανον εἰς τοὺς ἄνθρακας. Καὶ ὡσφράνθη Κύριος ὁ Θεὸς ὄσμην εὐωδίας. Ἔλαμψε δὲ τότε ὁ ναὸς ὅλος, καὶ ἤστραψεν ἐπάνω εἰς τὸν θόλον ὁ Παντοκράτωρ μὲ τὴν μεγάλην κ' ἐπιβλητικὴν μορφήν, καὶ ἠκτινοβόλησε τὸ ἐπίχρυσον καὶ λεπτοουργημένον μὲ μυρίας γλυφὰς τέμπλον, μὲ τὰς περικαλλεῖς τῆς ἀρίστης βυζαντινῆς τέχνης εἰκόνας του, μὲ τὴν μεγάλην εἰκόνα τῆς Γεννήσεως, ὅπου «Παρθένος καθέζεται τὰ Χερουβεὶμ μιμουμένη», ὅπου θεσπεσίως μαρμαίρουσιν αἱ μορφαὶ τοῦ θεοῦ Βρέφους καὶ τῆς ἀμώμου Λεχοῦς, ὅπου ζωντανὰ παρίστανται αἱ ὄψεις τῶν ἀγγέλων, τῶν μάγων καὶ τῶν ποιμένων, ..., καὶ ὅπου, ὡς ἐὰν ἡ γραφικὴ ἐλάλει, φαντάζεται τις ἐπὶ μίαν στιγμὴν ὅτι ἀκούει τό, Δόξα ἐν ὑψίστοις Θεῷ!»

{ “...and they loaded up the big portable stove, which had been being kept in the Sacred Bema, with charcoal, and they put it in the middle of the Temple, having previously sprinkled the charcoal with plenty of incense. And, the Lord sensed a smell of spiritual aroma. It was then that the interior of the Church shined thoroughly; the huge and impressive figure of the Pantocrator flashed from the Dome and the gilded, delicately-crafted and richly elegantly sculptured Iconostasis glowed holding its beauteous Byzantine Culture. Especially, the sizeable Icon of the Nativity: In which the Theotokos is seated imitating the Cherubim in the way they are honouring the swaddled and Phatne-accommodated newborn Theanthropos; from the Holy Infant and His Immaculate Mother-in-flesh of which heavenly successive scintillations are being emitted; to the live motion of the synthesis of which the Angels, the Shepherds and the Magi are actively contributing: ...: and by virtue of which the observer, being enlightened, is conceiving the Iconography as chanting the Glorification of God.” }

Such periodically offered pauses of transmission of radiated heavenly luminescence are conceived by the present Study as aimed by the Divine Providence at allowing for, welcoming and appreciating any potential event of volitional and ultimately enthusiastic conjunction of pure inward

accommodation and spontaneous outward expression of Devoutness being achieved by a free-Conscience Worshipper or Pilgrim, and, furthermore, at ethically rewarding such a resonant Psyche (after an adequate succession of pause pulses) by the completion of Catharsis and sacred Ecstasy.

**The Byzantine-Culture Paradigm of the Icon of the Nativity of Christ the Saviour
prevailing to-date ever since the 9th Century A.C. .**

This aesthetic and metaphysical analysis of the Icon of the Nativity provided by Alexander Papadiamantes, apart from revealing, according to the interpretation of the current Study, the contribution of a (subconscious) functionality of notional Physics to the overall creativity and piety of his Personality, is initially reminiscent of the Proem of the Kontakion of Christmas produced by the ecumenically respected, gifted Byzantine Hymnographer Saint Romanus the Melodist (490 – 556 A.C.), the “Pindar of Christian Rhythmic Poetry”:

Ἡ παρθένος σήμερον * τὸν ὑπερούσιον τίκτει,/ καὶ ἡ γῆ τὸ
σπήλαιον * τῷ ἀπροσίτῳ προσάγει! ἄγγελοι μετὰ ποιμένων *
δοξολογοῦσι,/ μάγοι δὲ μετὰ ἀστέρος * ὁδοιποροῦσι/
δι' ἡμᾶς γὰρ * ἐγεννήθη/ παιδίον νέον, * ὁ πρὸ αἰώνων Θεός.

{Today the Virgin has given birth to the Transcendent,/ and the Earth has brought the Cave to the Unreachable;/ Angels in common with Shepherds are praising Him,/ whilst the Magi, guided by the Star, are travelling towards Him;/ it is, indeed, for our sake that the older than Time eternal God/ has assumed the Human Flesh in becoming the newborn Infant. }

Icon (1649) of Saint Romanus the Melodist (Feast Day: 1st October) holding a scroll of his Kontakion of the Nativity and surrounded by the Patriarch, the Emperor and Members of the Ecclesia in the Temple of the Saint Wisdom of God (Hagia Sophia) of Constantinople. High above The Protection of the Mother of God, Hagia Skepe (Feast Day: 1st and additionally, for honouring the Thetokos as the miraculous Protector and Invincible Field-Marshal of the Hellenic National-Defence 1940-Epos, 28th October), having been being highly revered by the Melodist, is incorporated.

But yet, the historical fact that this Proem of the Christmas Kontakion by Romanus the Melodist has ultimately induced the Norm of the Byzantine Icon of the Nativity being taken into account, the present Study ventures to deduce that the exact style and emphasis of the Papadiamantean analysis of the Icon is a noteworthy reexamining of its Semantics and, even more, of vital facets of its Liturgical and Psyche-rejuvenating Message:

Now, the Interactivity between the Divinity and the Conscience of the observing Worshipper is focused upon by Papadiamantes in his feeling a Purpose underlying the modal duality of radiation of Heavenly Light, emitted, on the one hand, continually by the surroundings of the Icon (the shining interior of the Church), and, on the other, in a periodic pulse sequence by the very Icon (the Holy Infant and His Immaculate Mother-in-flesh) having been triggered by a single bright lightning-pulse flashed by the Pantocrator of the Dome.

Furthermore,

» *Όταν ἔφθασαν εἰς τὸ Κάστρον καὶ εἰσῆλθον εἰς τὸν ναὸν τοῦ Χριστοῦ, τόσον θάλπος ἐθώπευσε τὴν ψυχὴν των, ὥστε ἂν καὶ ἦσαν κατάκοποι, καὶ ἂν ἐνύσταζόν τινες αὐτῶν, ἠσθάνθησαν τόσον τὴν χαρὰν τοῦ ναὸς ζῶσι καὶ τοῦ ναὸς ἔχωσι φθάσει αἰσίως εἰς τὸ τέλος τῆς πορείας των, εἰς τὸν ναὸν τοῦ Κυρίου, ὥστε τοὺς ἔφυγε πᾶσα νύστα καὶ πᾶσα κόπωση. ...»*

{ *” Upon their ultimately arriving at the Castle and entering into the Temple of Christ, such warming sweetness caressed their Souls that, despite their being bodily worn out and even their having been drowsed by the heavy fatigue, they felt the joy of being alive and of having accomplished their Prayers-Promise; then all drowsing and weariness was immediately lifted away from them. ...” }*

It can, thus, be deduced, from the viewpoint of the present investigation, that the ethical sweetness experienced upon their successful arrival at the Citadel Church of the Nativity of Christ, especially as ignited by the impressive Metaphysical Scintillation of the Frescoes and the Temple Icons, is conceivable as a preciously rewarding non-material transmission of Heavenly appreciation for the Endeavour of willingly intensively keeping and applying their Hope of Faith.

In the following Subsection we are monitoring a second-stage observable effect of the Physico-Psychological Synergy having already allowed for the above Heavenly Antidosis concerning this Psychic Resonance of the Peregrine Worshippers.

2.2 Eucharistia in Christ and Common Table in Brotherhood

Scene of the first part of the Exodus of the Narrative Drama taking place during the Holy Communion and during the directly following preparation for and experiencing of the Christmas Common Table held in the Church forecourt in Christmas Day noon, the second part of the Exodus

being the tranquil-Sea naval travel of the Peregrine Worshippers' return to their Birthplace Village:

« ... Τέλος, εἰς τὸ «Μετὰ φόβου Θεοῦ», ἐπέστρεψαν πρῶτοι οἱ τελευταῖοι ἐξελθόντες πρὸς ἐπισκόπησιν, εἶτα εἰσῆλθεν ὁ μπαρμπα-Στεφανῆς καὶ οἱ μετ' αὐτοῦ καταβάντες εἰς τὸν αἰγιαλόν, καὶ μετ' αὐτὸν τρεῖς ἄγνωστοι μὲ ναυτικὰ ἐνδύματα ...»

» Ἐφεξεν ὁ Θεὸς τὴν χαρμόσυνον ἡμέραν, καὶ οἱ αἰπόλοι ἐφιλοτιμήθησαν νὰ σφάξωσι καὶ ψήσωσι δύο τρυφερὰ ἐρίφια, ... καὶ ὁ καπετὰν Κωσταντῆς , ἀνεβίβασε δύο ἀσκούς γενναίου οἴνου καὶ ἐν καλάθιον μὲ αὐγά Καὶ ἔφαγον πάντες καὶ ἠὺφράνθησαν, ἐορτάσαντες τὰ Χριστούγεννα μετὰ σπανίας μεγαλοπρεπείας ἐπὶ τοῦ ἐρήμου ἐκείνου βράχου....»

{“ ... Finally, whilst the Priest, the Reverend Francoules, is proceeding to the Devine Eucharistia and the small Flock are approaching him for the Holy Communion, there occur successively the relieving returns to the Temple of those of the Ecclesia having exited last for surveillance as to the origin of the calls for help, of Captain Stefanos escorted by those having followed him to the Seashore, and afterwards of three unknowns wearing nautical garments ...”

” God sent Light for the dawn of the Joyful Christmas Day, and the local Shepherds having already participated in the Ecclesia during the traditional nocturnal Nativity-Liturgy felt the spontaneous zeal of roasting two tender young goats over charcoal fire for the Feast's Common Table, ... ; and Constantes, the Captain of the Ship having been ultimately saved from being wrecked (thanks to having been guided at the last moment by the Light of the Torches having been ignited by the Excursionists around the Temple of the Nativity for honouring the religious Panegyris of the Christmas Liturgy), heartily brought two stout skins of brave wine and a basket of eggs And thusly all ate to their gleefulness, feasting Christmas in a rarely majestic manner on top of that deserted Sea-beaten, Sky-high Rock. ...” }

The present Study is, therefore, coming to conceive that the Excursionists' Psychic Resonance already established through the stimulus of the Metaphysical Scintillation of the Temple Icons has been persisting during the Christmas Liturgy and (has culminated at) the Divine Eucharistia, and has eventually blessedly given birth to a desire for and moral ability of their exhibiting Conjugate-Conscience Brotherhood around the Christmas Common Table.

We are, also, wishing to venture to attribute the unexpected epithet *ΓΕΝΝΑΙΟΣ* (“brave”) attached by Papadiamantes to *ΟΙΝΟΣ* (“wine”) in this Anthropomorphism (Figure of Speech by which an object or a non-human living being is presented by the Speaker / Rhetor or Writer as possessing or exhibiting a quality, functionality, feature pertaining to a human) to an idiosyncratic automation of his Personality by which a multifaceted notion is mentally shaped in tune with the ethical response (faster) produced by his Conscience harmonised with a potentially universally sound hierarchy of the entailed connotations: Bread and Wine being consecrated in Eucharistic Transubstantiation are acknowledged as the Brave Physical Substances serving as the Eucharistic Elements for the Holy Communion.

Commensurate to such an interpretation would be that through a different (from the above examined Anthropomorphism), singular Papadiamantean Figure of Speech (a kind of Catachrestic Synecdoche convoluted with a Liturgical Metaphor) “brave wine (of men)” is to be conceived as the “wine of brave men”, as the “wine being drunk by brave men”, by any Person, that is, bravely having decided to gain Catharsis and Purification deriving from properly receiving the Holy Communion.

The Post-1821 “Saint of the Hellenic Letters”, Alexander Papadiamantes (1851 – 1911)

3. Conclusion

The current Study has located and attempted to characterise major Signs of an idiosyncratic and existentially original interweaving of (subconscious) functionality of notional Physics and genuine Piety in the Opus of Alexander Papadiamantes through investigating his celebrated Christmas Narrative “To The Christ Of The Castle” (1892).

It has thus been argued that the ethical sweetness experienced upon the successful arrival of the Heroes of the Essay at the historical Citadel Church of the Nativity of Christ, especially as induced by the impressive Metaphysical Scintillation of the Byzantine Icons of the Temple, has been conceived by Papadiamantes and has been earnestly connoted by his Narrative as a preciously rewarding non-material transmission of Heavenly appreciation for the Endeavour of willingly actively keeping and applying their Hope of Faith.

Furthermore, it has been put forward by the Interpretation that the Excursionists’ Psychic Resonance already established through the stimulus of the Metaphysical Scintillation of the Temple Icons has been persisting during the Christmas Liturgy and (has culminated at) the Divine Eucharistia, and has eventually blessedly given birth to a desire for and moral ability of their exhibiting Conjugate-Conscience Brotherhood around the Christmas Common Table.

It has been, also, discussed by this Study that even through some illuminated Figures of Speech the Intellectual and Faithful Personality of Papadiamantes may be expressing, in accordance to his clear-Conscience experiencing, a devoutness-promoting interweaving of (notional) Physics and Pure Metaphysics.

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